

Comprehensive Study on Manufacturing, Quality Assurance, Properties, and Applications of Geosynthetic Geomembranes

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Abstract:

This extensive investigation provides a comprehensive analysis of geosynthetic geomembranes, elucidating their pivotal role as impermeable membrane liners in various engineering and environmental applications. The review explores the properties, construction, and applications of prominent geomembranes, including HDPE, LLDPE, PVC, EPDM, RPE, RPP, and GCL, showcasing their versatility and adaptability. The manufacturing process, from raw material preparation to final product formation, is detailed, emphasizing the intricate procedures involved in producing geomembranes with diverse dimensions. The paper underscores the critical significance of quality assurance and control in geomembrane manufacturing, outlining essential tests for uniformity, strength, puncture resistance, and impermeability. In addition, key manufacturers and suppliers in the field are highlighted, offering practical insights for professionals and researchers involved in diverse engineering projects. As the demand for effective fluid containment, environmental protection, and sustainable infrastructure continues to grow, this review serves as a valuable reference, providing a nuanced understanding of geomembranes and their applications in contemporary engineering practices.

Keywords: Fluid Containment, Geomembrane, Geosynthetic, Impermeable Barrier, Synthetic Membrane, Technical Textile.

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1. Introduction

Geotextile geomembranes, commonly referred to as geomembranes, have emerged as pivotal components in contemporary civil engineering and geotechnical practices. These specialized synthetic membranes serve the essential purpose of meticulously controlling the movement of fluids, rendering them indispensable in a diverse range of construction and environmental protection applications [1]. Over the years, the nomenclature surrounding geomembranes has evolved, encompassing terms such as synthetic membranes, polymeric membranes, plastic liners, flexible membrane liners, impermeable membranes, and impervious sheets. In this comprehensive examination, we employ the term "geomembrane" as the standardized reference for these impermeable membrane liners, primarily composed of polymeric materials. They are available in nonreinforced or reinforced composite variants, offering remarkable versatility in their applications. Their chemical composition endows them with remarkable impermeability, enabling compatibility with various materials, including rocks, earth, and soils. Furthermore, geomembranes can be effectively integrated into capping systems, where they serve as impermeable layers, enhancing security in diverse construction scenarios [2]. Geomembranes display multifaceted functionality, acting as reinforcements, filters, and separators, catering to the specific demands of each project. The impermeable nature of geomembranes makes them an ideal solution for the containment and management of fluids in various construction contexts. They have found extensive application in mining operations, playing crucial roles in lining solution and evaporation ponds, tailings impoundments, waste management, and water resource management [3]. Furthermore, geomembranes play a pivotal role in landfill barrier systems, where they emerge as cost-effective solutions for the containment of municipal solid waste, effectively addressing environmental concerns.

This review paper aims to delve into the extensive body of research and applications surrounding geomembranes, shedding light on their diverse uses, material properties, and the pivotal role they play in civil engineering, geotechnical engineering, and environmental protection.

2. Construction, Properties, and Applications of Various Geomembranes

The selection and specification of a geomembrane for a specific application necessitate a deep understanding of the properties of the various geomembranes specially the polymer used in its manufacture. These properties, such as flexibility, UV resistance, and thickness, greatly influence ease of installation and expected service life. The types of geomembranes with their construction, properties and applications are explain below.

2.1 High-density Polyethylene (HDPE) Geomembranes

2.1.1 Construction: HDPE geomembranes are engineered from high-density polyethylene, a thermoplastic crystalline polymer known for its robust construction and dense molecular structure [4]. Typically, these geomembranes contain a small percentage of carbon black, usually ranging from 2 to 3 percent, which enhances their resistance to ultraviolet (UV) radiation. The manufacturing process involves the extrusion of HDPE material into large sheets or rolls, which can be customized to various dimensions, thicknesses, and collars, which facilitates easier installation [5].

2.1.2 Properties: HDPE geomembranes are distinguished within the polyethylene family for their superior chemical resistance, a characteristic derived from their dense molecular structure. They feature factory-quality welds created through hot wedge and extrusion welding methods, which are often stronger than the geomembrane sheet itself [1]. The marketplace benefits from rigorous quality control and quality assurance testing, ensuring their reliability. Furthermore, their inherent UV stability eliminates the necessity for additional liner coverage, making them a cost-effective choice. HDPE geomembranes are available in roll stock, with thickness options spanning from 20 to 120 mil, catering to diverse project specifications.

2.1.3 Applications: HDPE geomembranes offer versatile solutions with applications in a wide array of settings. They are prominently utilized in critical water management infrastructure, including irrigation ponds, canals, ditches, and water reservoirs, where their impermeable properties are crucial [5]. In the mining industry, HDPE geomembranes play a vital role in heap leach and slag tailing ponds, ensuring the safe containment of mining byproducts and preventing environmental contamination. Beyond their utilitarian applications, HDPE geomembranes contribute to aesthetically focused projects, enhancing landscapes with their use in golf course and decorative ponds [6].

2.2 Linear Low-density Polyethylene (LLDPE) Geomembranes

2.2.1 Construction: LLDPE geomembranes are manufactured from a thermoplastic polymer with a lower density than High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE). These geomembranes are produced through an extrusion process, involving the melting of the polymer and shaping it into large sheets or rolls. Notably, LLDPE geomembranes are recognized for their flexibility, rendering them more manageable and easier to install compared to their high-density counterparts. Furthermore, they are available in various sizes, textures, and thickness options, offering flexibility to cater to diverse construction and environmental needs [7].

2.2.2 Properties: LLDPE geomembranes exhibit exceptional flexibility, allowing them to conform to uneven surfaces and adapt to changes in ground contours. This inherent characteristic makes them particularly well-suited for applications where differential settlements or rough subgrade conditions are anticipated. Additionally, LLDPE geomembranes offer impressive puncture resistance, ensuring the integrity of containment systems even in challenging environmental conditions. While LLDPE geomembranes are more flexible, it's worth noting that they have slightly lower tensile strength when compared to HDPE geomembranes [1]. Notably, LLDPE geomembrane seams can be thermally welded, creating strong and secure connections between sheets, thereby ensuring the overall integrity of containment systems.

2.2.3 Applications: LLDPE geomembranes find extensive application in a diverse range of industries, showcasing their remarkable versatility. They are crucial components in animal waste containment systems, where they serve as impermeable liners, effectively preventing the migration of contaminants into the surrounding soil and groundwater. In the mining sector, LLDPE geomembranes are pivotal in the construction and management of heap leach and slag tailings ponds, providing essential containment solutions for waste materials and process fluids. Furthermore, LLDPE geomembranes contribute to the aesthetic appeal of golf courses and landscaping projects by serving as liners for decorative ponds and water features. These geomembranes also ensure the secure storage of various liquids, including industrial and agricultural chemicals, in liquid storage tanks. Moreover, LLDPE geomembranes are deployed in applications involving brine solutions, industrial process waters, and diverse liquid containment scenarios, serving as reliable and impermeable barriers. In the realm of environmental protection, LLDPE geomembranes play a pivotal role in containment projects focused on isolating and controlling contaminants, thereby facilitating soil and groundwater remediation efforts aimed at mitigating environmental impacts [5].

2.3 Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) Geomembrane

2.3.1 Construction: PVC geomembranes are synthetic membranes made from a combination of high-quality polyvinyl chloride (PVC) resin, plasticizers, and additives. They are manufactured through extrusion or calendaring processes, resulting in a continuous, flat sheet of the desired thickness and width. PVC geomembranes are characterized by their flexibility, durability, and chemical resistance, making them ideal for a wide range of construction and environmental applications [8].

2.3.2 Properties: PVC geomembranes exhibit a range of desirable properties that make them highly effective in various applications. Their exceptional flexibility allows them to conform to irregular terrain contours and adapt to diverse construction needs, making them advantageous in situations anticipating differential settlements or rough subgrade conditions. The durability of PVC geomembranes is noteworthy, as they can withstand extreme temperatures, UV exposure, and chemical attack, ensuring prolonged performance in demanding environmental conditions. The chemical resistance of PVC geomembranes is also significant, as they are compatible with a broad range of liquids and gases, including chemicals, acids, and hydrocarbons, making them suitable for applications involving exposure to corrosive or hazardous substances. Additionally, PVC geomembranes possess other beneficial properties such as strong mechanical strength, abrasion resistance, and ease of welding, making them versatile for a wide array of containment and environmental protection applications. In essence, the combination of flexibility, durability, chemical resistance, and other commendable attributes positions PVC geomembranes as versatile and reliable materials for a multitude of construction and environmental protection purposes [8].

2.3.3 Applications: PVC geomembranes are versatile materials with a wide range of applications across diverse industries. In environmental containment systems, such as landfill liners, covers, and caps, PVC geomembranes play a crucial role in preventing the migration of contaminants into the surrounding soil and groundwater. This application is vital for environmental protection. Additionally, these geomembranes are employed to line potable water reservoirs, ensuring the safe storage of drinking water due to their chemical resistance and durability. Furthermore, PVC geomembranes are effective linings for tanks used to store various liquids, including industrial and agricultural chemicals, wastewater, and potable water. Their use extends to secondary containment systems, where they play a crucial role in safeguarding against leaks and spills of hazardous substances [8].

2.3 Ethylene Propylene-diene Monomers (EPDM)

2.4.1 Construction: Ethylene Propylene-diene Monomers (EPDM) geomembranes are synthetic rubber membranes that offer exceptional weather resistance and durability. They are manufactured through a blending and compounding process that vulcanizes ethylene, propylene, and diene monomers to create a thermoset rubber. This process imparts the geomembrane with its unique properties, including flexibility across a wide temperature range and outstanding resistance to UV exposure [9].

2.4.2 Properties: EPDM geomembranes possess several advantageous characteristics that make them well-suited for a variety of construction and environmental applications. Notably, their exceptional flexibility, even at low temperatures, makes them ideal for scenarios where they need to conform to irregular terrain contours or undergo repeated bending and folding. The UV resistance of EPDM geomembranes ensures their suitability for outdoor applications, providing durability in the face of prolonged sun exposure. In terms of durability, EPDM geomembranes exhibit resilience to various environmental conditions, including extreme temperatures, chemical attack, and mechanical stress. This durability factor contributes to their long-term performance in demanding applications. Additionally, the chemical resistance of EPDM geomembranes, compatible with a wide range of liquids and gases, including chemicals, acids, and hydrocarbons, positions them as an ideal choice for applications involving exposure to corrosive or hazardous substances. In summary, the flexibility, UV resistance, durability, and chemical resistance of EPDM geomembranes collectively make them a reliable and versatile material for various construction and environmental protection needs.

2.4.3 Applications: EPDM geomembranes find diverse applications in construction and environmental engineering, showcasing their versatility and reliability. Widely utilized in water containment systems, these geomembranes serve as liners for irrigation ponds, canals, reservoirs, and ditches. Additionally, they play a crucial role in lining potable water reservoirs and drinking water storage tanks. In agricultural settings, EPDM geomembranes are employed to line and cover agricultural ponds and containment structures, including fish ponds and tanks. Beyond water-related applications, EPDM geomembranes contribute to landscaping endeavours by serving as liners for golf courses and decorative ponds. In environmental remediation projects, these geomembranes are utilized as protective barriers to address soil remediation needs. Moreover, EPDM geomembranes find application in various other contexts, such as secondary containment systems, mining applications, and landfill closures, as highlighted by. This broad range of applications underscores the adaptability and effectiveness of EPDM geomembranes in meeting the diverse needs of construction and environmental engineering projects [9].

2.4 Reinforced Polyethylene (RPE) Geomembrane

2.5.1 Construction: Reinforced Polyethylene (RPE) geomembranes are a versatile and durable type of geomembrane that is widely used in construction projects. They are constructed with meticulous attention to detail, featuring a robust polyethylene fabric with either an HDPE or LDPE coating. This unique combination of materials creates an impermeable barrier capable of securely containing liquids, solids, or sludge in various construction and environmental applications. RPE geomembranes are crafted to provide resilience in challenging conditions, ensuring durability and long-term performance [10].

2.5.2 Properties: RPE geomembranes possess a unique combination of properties that make them particularly well-suited for a diverse range of containment and environmental protection applications. These geomembranes are characterized by their exceptional flexibility and adaptability to varying terrain contours, ensuring a secure and impermeable barrier. They offer outstanding resistance to UV radiation, chemicals, and even oils, which contributes to their longevity and effectiveness in harsh conditions. RPE geomembranes remain durable even when exposed to challenging environmental factors, such as extreme temperatures, fluctuating water levels, and mechanical stress. Their ability to be prefabricated into large panels, which reduces the number of seams required during installation, enhances their efficiency and reliability. Furthermore, their adaptability to varying thicknesses, ranging from 12 to 36 mil, ensures they can cater to specific project requirements. The convenience of on-site repairs and their fast installation capabilities make them well-suited for emergency applications [10].

2.5.3 Applications: RPE geomembranes, featuring a sturdy polyethylene fabric with HDPE or LDPE coating, exhibit exceptional versatility for diverse construction and environmental settings. These geomembranes securely contain substances like contaminated soils, liquids, and sludge. Specifically, RPE geomembranes excel in lining temporary retaining ponds for water storage in construction or environmental projects, boasting durability and UV resistance for prolonged exposure. In soil remediation, they play a crucial role in constructing pads to treat contaminated soils, effectively containing contaminants and preventing leaching into the environment. In summary, the robust qualities of RPE geomembranes make them indispensable for secure containment and management of various substances in different construction and environmental contexts [10, 11].

2.6 Geosynthetic Clay Liners (GCL)

2.6.1 Construction: Geosynthetic Clay Liners (GCLs) are a type of geomembrane that is constructed by sandwiching a layer of processed sodium bentonite between two geotextile layers. When exposed to moisture, the bentonite swells and forms a low-permeability clay liner, effectively preventing the seepage of liquids and contaminants. GCLs are widely used in construction applications where impermeable containment and environmental protection are essential [12].

2.6.2 Properties: Geosynthetic Clay Liners (GCLs) exhibit a unique set of properties that render them highly suitable for a diverse range of containment and environmental protection applications. Their inherent impermeability, even in the presence of hydraulic gradients, makes them ideal for preventing liquid and contaminant seepage. Notably, GCLs are characterized by durability, showcasing resistance to physical and chemical degradation, ensuring their long-term effectiveness in harsh environmental conditions. The flexibility of GCLs is another notable attribute, allowing them to easily adapt to uneven surfaces and facilitating straightforward installation. Additionally, GCLs offer a cost-effective alternative to traditional clay liners while delivering comparable performance, further enhancing their appeal in various applications. In essence, the impermeability, durability, flexibility, and cost-effectiveness of GCLs collectively contribute to their effectiveness in meeting the stringent requirements of containment and environmental protection initiatives [12].

2.6.3 Applications: Geosynthetic Clay Liners (GCLs) are widely employed in diverse construction applications, showcasing their versatility and effectiveness. In landfill management, GCLs serve as impermeable liners and covers, preventing leachate seepage into the environment. For dams and reservoirs, GCLs offer a reliable solution to prevent seepage and protect water quality. Similarly, they are utilized in canals and ponds to maintain water levels and prevent seepage. In agriculture, GCLs find use in lining ponds and manure storage facilities. In mining and industrial settings, GCLs play a crucial role in lining pits and waste containment facilities, preventing the infiltration of hazardous materials into the soil and groundwater. The applications extend to diverse contexts, including golf courses, decorative ponds, and slag tailings, highlighting the broad utility of GCLs in meeting impermeability and containment requirements across various construction and environmental scenarios [13].

3. Manufacturing Process of Geomembranes

The manufacturing process of polymeric geomembranes involves a series of sequential operations to create these essential materials used in waste containment, environmental protection, and civil engineering projects.

3.1 Raw material preparation: The process begins with the preparation of raw materials, including polymer resin and various additives such as antioxidants, plasticizers, fillers, carbon black, and lubricants. These additives are carefully selected to impart specific properties to the geomembranes, such as UV resistance, flexibility, and chemical stability.

3.2 Formulation: The combination of polymer resin and additives forms the "formulation" for the geomembrane, defining its characteristics and performance attributes.

3.3 Extrusion: For certain geomembranes, particularly HDPE, LLDPE, and polypropylene, the extrusion method is employed. In this step, a molten polymeric compound is extruded through a die to create a continuous sheet of polymeric material. Blown film extrusion, cast extrusion, and extrusion coating are sub-methods within this stage, each offering unique advantages. Blown film extrusion, for instance, provides biaxial orientation for improved tear resistance.

3.4 Texturing: Texturing is a critical step in enhancing the frictional properties and sliding resistance of geomembranes. Various methods, such as coextrusion, impingement, lamination, and structuring, are employed during or after extrusion to achieve the desired surface texture.

3.5 Calendaring: Another manufacturing method, especially applicable to PVC, CSPE, and reinforced geomembranes, is calendaring. In this step, the polymeric compound is passed through a series of heated rollers, forming a polymeric sheet. Calendaring can produce multi-ply geomembranes with complementary properties, and textured surfaces can be achieved using patterned rollers.

3.6 Final product formation: The extruded or calendared sheets serve as the foundation for the final geomembrane product. Depending on the application and specific requirements, the sheets may undergo additional processes or be combined to create multi-ply geomembranes [4].

4. Quality Assurance and Control in Geomembrane Manufacturing

Quality assurance and control are integral components of geomembrane manufacturing, ensuring the reliability and performance of these crucial products [14]. Geomembranes play a pivotal role in various applications, including environmental protection, waste containment, and liquid storage, where their impermeability is essential. By implementing rigorous quality assurance and control processes, manufacturers can verify that their geomembranes meet stringent standards and regulations. This is of utmost importance, as it safeguards safety, prevents environmental contamination, and reduces the risk of costly failures. In geomembrane manufacturing range of essential tests involves to ensure the reliability and performance of these critical products. These tests include [14, 15]:

- Thickness measurements: To verify the uniformity of the geomembrane.
- Seam strength tests: To assess the quality of welded or bonded seams.
- Tensile strength tests: To determine the geomembrane's ability to withstand mechanical stress.
- Puncture resistance tests: To gauge its ability to resist damage.
- Permeability tests: To assess the impermeability of the geomembrane, ensuring that it effectively prevents liquid or gas seepage.
- Tests for UV resistance and environmental stress cracking: To evaluate the geomembrane's durability in various conditions.

5. Manufacturers and Suppliers of Geomembrane

5.1 Manufacturers

- GSE Environmental, Website: <http://gseinc.com>
GSE Environmental is a global manufacturer known for producing geomembranes, geonets, and geosynthetic clay liners. They offer a wide range of geosynthetic solutions for environmental and civil engineering applications.
- Solmax: Website: <https://www.solmax.com>
Solmax is a prominent manufacturer specializing in high-quality geomembranes and related geosynthetic products. They provide innovative solutions for a variety of applications in the geosynthetics industry.
- Raven Industries: Website: <https://ravenfd.com>
Raven Industries is involved in the production of various geomembranes, including high-density polyethylene (HDPE) geomembranes. Their products are used in a wide range of applications, from agriculture to environmental protection.
- NAUE Geosynthetics: Website: <https://www.naue.com>
NAUE Geosynthetics is a company that specializes in geosynthetic solutions, offering geomembranes, geotextiles, geogrids, and other products for soil stabilization, environmental protection, and civil engineering projects.
- Agru America: Website: <https://www.agruamerica.com>
Agru America is a manufacturer that produces various geomembranes, including HDPE and LLDPE geomembranes. Their geomembranes find application in sectors such as environmental protection, waste containment, and industrial applications.

5.2 Suppliers and Distributors:

- Geosynthetics Limited: Website: <https://www.geosyn.co.uk>
Geosynthetics Limited is a UK-based company that supplies and distributes a wide range of geosynthetic materials, including geomembranes. They serve various industries with geosynthetic solutions.
- HUESKER: Website: <https://www.huesker.com>

HUESKER is a global geosynthetic engineering company offering a range of geosynthetic products, including geomembranes. Their products are used in applications related to geotechnical engineering and environmental protection.

- Titan Environmental Containment: Website: <https://www.titanenviro.com>

Titan Environmental Containment is a North American supplier specializing in geosynthetics, including geomembranes. They cater to various projects in the fields of environmental and civil engineering.

- Geosynthetics, Inc.: Website: <https://www.geosynthetics.net>

Geosynthetics, Inc. is a U.S.-based company that supplies geosynthetic products, including geomembranes, to a wide range of industries. Their products are used in applications such as waste containment and soil reinforcement.

6. Conclusions

This comprehensive investigation provides a thorough exploration of the crucial role played by geosynthetic geomembranes in contemporary engineering and environmental practices. Geomembranes, as impermeable membrane liners, serve as indispensable components in a myriad of applications, including waste management, mining, water containment, and construction. The review delves into the properties, construction, and applications of various types of geomembranes, such as HDPE, LLDPE, PVC, EPDM, RPE, RPP, and GCL, highlighting their versatility and adaptability. The manufacturing process, from raw material preparation to final product formation, is elucidated, emphasizing the intricacies involved in producing geomembranes of varying dimensions and specifications.

Furthermore, the paper underscores the paramount importance of quality assurance and control in geomembrane manufacturing, elucidating the battery of tests conducted to ensure uniformity, strength, puncture resistance, and impermeability. The inclusion of key manufacturers and suppliers in the field enhances the practical utility of the review, providing valuable information for professionals and researchers engaged in the design and implementation of diverse engineering projects.

As we look to the future, with increasing demands for fluid containment, environmental protection, and sustainable infrastructure, geomembranes stand out as critical components within the realm of geosynthetic materials. This review serves as a comprehensive reference, offering insights into the multifaceted functionalities and applications of geomembranes, as well as the meticulous processes involved in their creation. By illuminating the diverse landscape of geomembranes, this paper contributes to the collective knowledge base, empowering practitioners to make informed decisions in their pursuit of effective and sustainable engineering solutions.

References:

- [1] D. Smith, "Quality assurance for geosynthetics" *Geosynthetics in Civil Engineering*, 2006, 233-243, <https://doi.org/10.1533/9781845692490.2.233>
- [2] S. Manan, J. Pitroda, and J. J. Bhavsar, "HDPE geomembranes: A liner material for reservoirs," *International Conference on: Engineering: Issues, opportunities and Challenges for Development*, April, 2015, 1-12
- [3] L. Zhou, Z. Zhu, Z. Yu, and C. Zhang, "Shear testing of the interfacial friction between an HDPE geomembrane and solid waste," *Materials*, Vol. 13, Issue 7, April 2020, doi: 10.3390/ma13071672
- [4] J. Scheirs, "HDPE Geomembranes", *A Guide to Polymeric Geomembranes*, 2009, 21-51. doi: 10.1002/9780470748213.fmatter
- [5] K. H. Lou, A. Tay, and C. S. Lim, "New developments in polyethylene materials for geomembrane applications," *11th International Conference on Geosynthetics*, September 2018, 16-21
- [6] H. B. Ng and C. Qi, "HDPE geomembrane applications in high altitude region," *5th Asian Regional Conference on Geosynthetics: Geosynthetics for Sustainable Adaptation to Climate Change*, December 2012, 843-850
- [7] C. West, "Structured geomembrane liners in mining base and closure systems," *SME Annual Meeting and Exhibit and CMA 113th National Western Mining Conference*, May 2011, 9-12
- [8] A. Luciani, C. Todaro, D. Martinelli, and D. Peila, "Long-term durability assessment of PVC-P waterproofing geomembranes through laboratory tests," *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, vol. 103, September 2020, 1-11, doi: 10.1016/j.tust.2020.103499
- [9] A. Kumar, R. Choudhary, and A. Kumar, "Characterisation of asphalt binder modified with ethylene-propylene-diene-monomer (EPDM) rubber waste from automobile industry," *Road Materials and Pavement Design*, Vol. 22, Issue 9, March 2021, 1-25, doi: 10.1080/14680629.2020.1740772

- [10] I. D. Peggs, "Factors influencing the durability of polypropylene geomembranes: The goal Being an Effective Specification," *Geosynthetics Research and Development in Progress*, May 2012, 1-12. doi: 10.1061/40782(161)59
- [11] M. Sadlier and R. Frobel, "Current developments and trends for water reservoir renovation with geosynthetics," *11th International Conference on Geosynthetics*, 2018, 1-7
- [12] G. Heerten, "Geosynthetic clay liner performance in geotechnical applications", *Clay Geosynthetic Barriers*, 2022, 70-87, doi: 10.1201/9781003078777-1
- [13] R. K. Rowe, "Geosynthetic clay liners: Perceptions and misconceptions," *Geotextiles and Geomembranes*, Vol. 48, Issue 2, April 2020, 137-156, doi: 10.1016/j.geotextmem.2019.11.012
- [14] D. Smith, "Quality assurance for geosynthetics", *Geosynthetics in civil engineering*, 2007, 233-242, doi: 10.1201/9781439824290.ch11
- [15] H. Zanzinger, "Quality assurance in the manufacture and installation of GCLs", *Geosynthetic Clay Liners*, 2020, 335-345. doi: 10.1201/9781003077848-24